

Comparative evaluation of the effects of number and distribution of implants upon in vitro dislodging forces to a simulated implant supported overdenture and to examine difference between two different attachment systems: An in vitro study.

Saurabh Pratap Singh¹, Rahul Nagrath², Manesh Lahori³, Siddharth Sisodiya², Prerna Kaushik⁴, Shikha Shahi⁵.

¹Senior Lecturer, Dept. Of Prosthodontics, K.D. Dental College & Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

²Professor, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

³Dean and Head, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

⁴Reader, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

⁵Post graduate student, Department of Prosthodontics, K. D. Dental College and Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Abstract

Background: Edentulous patients often face challenges with conventional mandibular complete dentures, including poor stability, retention, and compromised masticatory function, leading to discomfort and dissatisfaction. Implant-retained overdentures offer a promising solution, improving function and comfort. Two-implant-supported mandibular overdentures have become the standard of care due to their cost-effectiveness and favorable outcomes compared to fixed implant prostheses.

Objective: This study aims to evaluate the impact of varying implant numbers and their distribution on dislodging forces of implant-supported overdentures, comparing the performance of ball and locator attachment systems in vitro.

Methodology: An ideal mandibular stone cast was used to fabricate a denture, and implant analogs were placed in various locations of the cast. Ball and locator attachment systems were installed on the analogs. The study assessed four groups with different numbers of implants (1 to 4) across nine locations on the mandible. The overdenture was tested for dislodging forces in three directions: vertical, anteroposterior, and oblique, using a Universal Testing Machine (UTM).

Results: The study found that increased implant numbers and optimal distribution of implants improved retention. Locator attachments provided superior retention under vertical dislodgement, while ball attachments performed better under oblique and anteroposterior forces. The highest retention was observed in four-implant-supported overdentures, particularly in the IV-CA/P2 region.

Conclusion: The study concluded that both implant number and distribution significantly affect overdenture retention. Locator attachments were superior to ball attachments in all positions tested, particularly for vertical dislodgement. The findings suggest that the OD-1 protocol, with implants placed in the canine and second premolar positions, offers an effective and cost-effective solution for implant-supported overdentures.

Keywords: Ball attachments, Implant-supported overdentures, Locator attachments, Prosthetic retention, Universal Testing Machine.

Address of correspondence: Dr. Saurabh Pratap Singh, Senior Lecturer, Dept. Of Prosthodontics, K.D. Dental College & Hospital, Mathura, Uttar Pradesh, India.

Email address: - sautabhpratapsingh1234@gmail.com **Phone no:** 9808822499. **DOI:** 10.5281/zenodo.15557289

Submitted: 29-Mar-2025 **Revised:** 10-Apr-2025 **Accepted:** 30-Apr-2025 **Published:** 31-May-2025

Bibliographic details: Journal of Orofacial Rehabilitation Vol. 5(1), May 2025, pp. 12-23.

Introduction

Edentulous patients frequently experience issues with conventional mandibular complete dentures, including poor stability, reduced

retention, and compromised masticatory function. These factors contribute to patient dissatisfaction and discomfort.^[1] To address these concerns, implant-retained overdentures

were introduced and have shown significant improvement in function and comfort over the past two decades.

Although many edentulous individuals adapt to traditional dentures, a subset experiences persistent problems such as pain during chewing and limited retention. Implant-retained overdentures offer a viable solution, enhancing oral function and potentially preserving residual ridge structure.^[2] Two-implant-supported mandibular overdentures are now widely regarded as the standard of care due to their simplicity, cost-effectiveness, and favourable outcomes comparable to fixed implant prostheses.^[3]

Key determinants of overdenture success include retention, support, and stability. Various attachment systems have been studied, including ball and locator attachments.^[4] Locator attachments, while more expensive, provide better alignment, retention, and are particularly advantageous in cases of implant angulation. In contrast, ball attachments are more economical and suited for narrow ridges but have a higher profile, which may be less desirable.^[5]

Despite numerous studies, limited data exist on the optimal number and distribution of implants for overdenture retention. The present investigation aims to evaluate, *in vitro*, the dislodgement forces associated with different implant positions and numbers—ranging from single to four implants—placed in various mandibular locations (central incisor to second premolar), using both locator and ball attachments.

Aim

The aim of this study is to evaluate and compare the influence of varying implant numbers and their distribution on the dislodging forces of a simulated implant-

supported overdenture *in vitro*, and to assess the differences between two distinct attachment systems.

Methodology

METHOD OF CAST FABRICATION:

An ideal mandibular stone cast (Figure 1) was used to fabricate mould by using thermoplastic sheet of 2 mm (Figure 2) (SCHEU DENTAL TECHNOLOGY) using SCHEU MINISTAR MACHINE (Figure 3 and 4).

After mould formation, a cast was made using clear self cure acrylic resin (DPI). Later, acrylic mandibular cast was removed from the mould and finishing and polishing was done. This acrylic cast would serve as the model for overdenture fabrication (Figure 5).

Fabrication of denture

Ideal edentulous cast was made by dental stone in silicon mould. Denture base made on the ideal stone cast by autopolymerising resin and wax rims were fabricated on the denture base and arbitrary rim relation mounted on the three-pin articulator. Teeth arrangement (teeth set acrylic ms25) was done on the same mandibular maxillary stone cast and complete denture was allowed to cure by using heat cure acrylic resin (trevalon). After finishing and polishing, denture was placed on acrylic cast (Figure 6 and 7).

Preparation of mandibular cast for implant analogue placement

Ney surveyor was used to mark purchase point on the cast on the designated areas. Hand piece was attached to the vertical arm and cast was placed on the table of surveyor (Figure 8 and 9). Straight fissure bur was used to drill at the previously marked designated areas of simulated osteotomy sites. This allowed the

surveyor to incorporate correct orientation and parallelism (Figure 10 and 11).

Placement of Implant Analogues in Mandibular Cast

Implant analogues were placed in the mandibular cast using autopolymerizing resin at the simulated osteotomy sites. Nine analogs were positioned at the following locations: central incisor, right and left lateral incisors, right and left canines, right and left 1st premolars, and right and left 2nd premolars (Figure 12).

Ball attachments were installed and tightened on the analogues using a hex and ratchet. Nylon caps were inserted into the metal housing, and the entire assembly was placed onto the ball attachment. A separating medium (nylon gloves) was used between the cast and denture.

On the intaglio surface of the denture, areas were marked, and acrylic burs were used to create space for the metal housings. Autopolymerizing resin was loaded into the created spaces, and the denture was placed on the cast, allowing the resin to set. Excess resin was trimmed, and the denture was finished and polished.

Placement of m-hook on denture

4 M hooks were placed on denture at the canine and 1st molar region by using straight fissure bur for drilling. Then, M hook were placed at the prepared site using auto polymerizing resin which was then allowed to set (Figure 13).

Platform for cast holder and dislodge unit

A 4"× 4" metal sheet of 1cm thickness was welded with 2cm × 10cm rod at 90degree. After the welding, metal sheet was allowed to lathe for uniform surface.

Effects of number and distribution of implants

2"× 2" metal sheet of 1cm thickness was welded with 2cm × 10cm long rod at 90 degree and four holes were drilled at every corner. A 30 cm long stainless chain was welded to these holes for dislodgement of denture. This assembly was customized to be used in the UTM machine.

MEASUREMENT OF DISLODGING FORCES

Total two types of implant overdenture attachments were selected for the study ball and socket attachment and locator attachment. Nine sites were designated which are as follows:

1. In between the central incisors
2. Right and left lateral incisors
3. Right and left canines
4. Right and left 1st premolar
5. Right and left 2nd premolars

Four groups were made on the basis of number of attachments used:

GROUP 1: one attachment

GROUP 2: two attachments

GROUP 3: three attachments

GROUP 4: four attachments

Group 1 had only single attachment system

Group 2 had 2 attachment as given below:

Canine (right and left)

Premolar 1st (right and left)

Premolar 2nd (right and left)

Group 3 had 3 attachments as given below:

Central incisor and right and left canine

Central incisor and right and left premolar 1st

Central incisor and right and left premolar 2nd

Group 4 had 4 attachments as given below:

Lateral incisors and canines (right and left)

Canines and premolar 1st (right and left)

Canines and premolar 2nd (right and left)

Denture was dislodged by three directions of force:

1. Vertical dislodgement (Figure 14).
2. Anterio-posterior dislodgement (Figure 15 and 16).
3. Oblique dislodgement (Figure 17).

Cast was held on the lower chamber of UTM with the help of cast holder and dislodging unit was fixed on the upper chamber of the UTM (Figure 18). Denture was attached to the dislodging unit with the stainless steel chains and machine was allowed to dislodge the denture at 52 hrz frequency.

Result

Statistical Analysis
The data obtained in this study were analyzed to assess differences between groups using ball and locator attachment systems. One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) and post hoc Tukey's Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) test were employed to evaluate statistical significance.

ANOVA was used to determine overall variability both within and between the study groups. This test is an extension of the t-test, allowing for simultaneous comparison among more than two groups. Although ANOVA can indicate whether a statistically significant difference exists, it does not specify which groups differ from one another. Therefore,

post hoc analysis using Tukey's HSD test was conducted to identify the specific group pairs that showed significant differences.

Tukey's HSD test is a post hoc comparison method designed for pairwise analysis of group means, highlighting the precise subgroups where statistically significant differences occur.

Descriptive statistics, including mean values and standard deviations, were calculated for each group (Graphs 1 to 5).

All statistical evaluations were performed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS), version 17.0 for Windows. A significance level of 95% was adopted (P = 0.05).

P-value > 0.05: Not Significant (NS)

P-value < 0.05: Significant (S)

Discussion

Implant-supported overdentures provide a viable alternative to conventional dentures, addressing issues like retention, mucosal irritation, and masticatory inefficiency, improving the quality of life for edentulous patients. The McGill Consensus recommends two-implant-supported mandibular overdentures for their enhanced stability, retention, and bone preservation, especially in patients with poor denture-bearing anatomy or parafunctional habits. These overdentures can be fully implant-supported (RP-4) or a combination of implant and tissue support (RP-5), offering advantages like reduced bone loss and better aesthetics but also requiring strict hygiene and higher costs.

The OD-1 protocol, involving two implants placed in the B and D positions, is the gold standard for patients with minimal functional demands. Locator and ball attachments are commonly used. Locator attachments, with dual retention and angulation compensation,

provide superior retention, especially under vertical dislodgement forces.⁶ Ball attachments are more cost-effective and perform better under oblique or anteroposterior forces, though they may wear over time.^{7]}

In a comparative study evaluating the retentive characteristics of ball and locator attachments across varying implant positions, retention was assessed using a universal testing machine. The study revealed that locator attachments provided superior retention under vertical dislodgement forces, particularly in configurations with implants placed in the canine and second premolar regions (IV-CA/P2 and IV-CA/P1). Conversely, ball attachments demonstrated better performance under oblique and anteroposterior dislodging forces. Overall, increased retention correlated with a greater number of implants and their optimal spatial distribution. The findings suggested that two-implant overdentures placed in the canine and second premolar positions offer an effective and conservative solution with satisfactory retention outcomes.

Several studies have investigated the retentive performance of different overdenture attachment systems, providing a strong evidence base for clinical decision-making. **Scherer (2013)** emphasized that the number and spatial distribution of implants play a critical role in overdenture retention. He demonstrated that increasing the number of implants and placing them further apart improves mechanical stability, distributing dislodging forces more effectively and enhancing overall prosthesis retention. This finding supports the current study's observation that optimal implant distribution—such as placement in the canine and second premolar regions—yields superior retention outcomes.^[8] **Sadig (2009)** evaluated various overdenture attachments and reported that locator attachments produced the highest retentive forces among the systems tested.

This is consistent with the present study's results, which found locator attachments to be superior under vertical dislodging forces. The dual-retention design and angulation compensation of the locator system likely contribute to this performance, particularly in clinical scenarios with non-parallel implant positioning.^[9] **Michelinakis et al. (2006)** conducted a comparative in vitro study examining the retentive strengths of ball, bar, and magnetic attachments. Their results indicated that ball attachments provided the highest retention, whereas magnetic attachments showed the lowest. This partially aligns with the present findings, particularly under oblique and anteroposterior load directions, where ball attachments outperformed locator systems. These findings underscore the importance of selecting attachment systems based on the dominant functional forces in each patient case.^[10] In contrast, **Ahmadzadeh et al. (2012)** reported that castable attachments demonstrated greater retention than locator attachments. This result differs from the current study, which observed better retention values with locator systems in vertical dislodgement. Such discrepancies may be attributed to differences in study design, attachment wear, aging processes, or testing protocols.^[11] Collectively, these studies validate the multifactorial nature of attachment system performance and highlight the need for individualized treatment planning. The choice between locator and ball attachments should be based not only on their mechanical properties but also on patient-specific factors such as oral anatomy, prosthetic space, hygiene capacity, and implant angulation. Implant-supported mandibular overdentures using the OD-1 protocol provide a reliable and cost-effective treatment modality, especially when anatomical conditions are favourable and patient demands are minimal. Locator attachments are particularly effective in managing vertical dislodging forces and

angulation issues, while ball attachments may offer better retention in oblique and anteroposterior directions. The choice of attachment should be guided by anatomical, functional, and patient-specific considerations to ensure long-term success and patient satisfaction.

Conclusion

The study concluded that interimplant distance significantly affects overdenture retention. The highest retention was observed in four-implant-supported overdentures, particularly in the IV-CA/P2 region (mean: 10.49 N). Three-implant-supported overdentures also showed good retention at the III-CI/P2 site (mean: 7.8 N). Two implants placed in the canine (mean: 6.81 N) and second premolar regions (mean: 8.63 N) provided satisfactory results. Among the attachments, locators outperformed ball attachments in retention across all positions.

References

1. Carl mish 3rd editioncontamporay implant dentistry
2. Michael D. Scherer, MS1/Edwin A. McGlumphy, DDS, MS2/ Robert R. Seghi, DDS, Comparison of Retention and Stability of Implant-Retained Overdentures Based upon Implant Number and DistributionInt J Oral MaxillofacIMplants 2013;28: - 10.11607
3. Rutkunas V, Mizutani H, Takahashi H. Influence of attachment wear on retention of mandibular overdenture. J Oral Rehabil 2007;34: 41–51.
4. Alan G. T. Payne, Mandibular Implant-Supported Overdentures: A Prospective Evaluation of the Burden of Prosthodontic Maintenance with 3 Different Attachment Systems Int J Prosthodont 2000;13:246–253.
5. Masahiro Tokuhisa, In Vitro Study of a Mandibular Implant Overdenture Retained with Ball, Magnet, or Bar Attachments: Comparison of Load Transfer and Denture Stability Int J Prosthodont 2003;16:128–134.
6. Sunyoung Ma et al-Maxillary Three-Implant OverdenturesOpposing Mandibular Two-Implant Overdentures: 10-Year Prosthodontic Outcomes, Int J Prosthodont 2016;29:327–336.
7. Kwok-Hung Chung, Dean Whiting; Retentive Characteristics of Overdenture Attachments During Repeated Dislodging and Cyclic Loading, Int J Prosthodont 2011;24:127–129.
8. Scherer MD, McGlumphy EA, Seghi RR, Campagni WV. Comparison of retention and stability of implant-retained overdentures based upon implant number and distribution. Int J Oral Maxillofac Implants 2013;28:1619–1628.
9. Trakas T, Michalakis K, Kang K, Hirayama H. Attachment systems for implant retained overdentures: A literature review. Implant Dent 2006;15:24–34
10. Michelinakis G, Barclay CW, Smith PW. The influence of interimplant distance and attachment type on the retention characteristics of mandibular overdentures on 2 implants: Initial retention values. Int J Prosthodont 2006;19:507–512.
11. Alsabeeha N, Atieh M, Swain MV, Payne AG. Attachment systems for mandibular single-implant overdentures: An in vitro retention force investigation on different designs. Int J Prosthodont 2010;23:160– 166.

TABLES

Graph-1 illustrate the difference between the peak vertical Load (N), peak oblique load (N), peak antero-posterior load (N) in ball attachment system. Vertical arm of graphs shows the displacement force and horizontal shows number of group.

Graph-2 illustrate the difference between the peak vertical Load (N), peak oblique load (N), peak antero-posterior load (N) in locator attachment system. Vertical arm of graphs shows the displacement force and horizontal shows number of group.

Graph-3 illustrate the difference between the peak vertical Load (N), in ball & locator attachment system. Vertical arm of graphs shows the displacement force and horizontal shows number of group.

Graph-4 illustrate the difference between the peak oblique Load (N), in ball & locator attachment system. Vertical arm of graphs shows the displacement force and horizontal shows number of group.

Graph-5 illustrate the difference between the peak anterior posterior Load (N) , in ball & locator attachment system. Vertical arm of graphs shows the displacement force and horizontal shows number of group.

FIGURES

Figure 1

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

Figure 5

Figure 6

Figure 7

Figure 8

Figure 9

Figure 10

Figure 11

Figure 12

Figure 13

Figure 14

Figure 15

Figure 16

Figure 17

Figure 18

